

gravimetric percent swelling (a) was calculated from the equation,

$$a = \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_d} \times 100$$

Swelling percentage for various samples are given in Table 1.

Attrition percentage: The percentage attrition of different samples was determined and compared with each other. The particles in each sample were separated into two sizes, >200 mesh and <200 mesh. Particles >200 mesh size were shaken for several hours and again the particles >200 mesh in size were separated. From the weights of the particles before and after shaking, the attrition effect was calculated for each sample and the values were compared (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The average percentage swelling decreases as the percentage of wheat husk charcoal in the resin increases. The swelling percentage of the pure resin is higher than other samples. As the charcoal is added, the porous nature decreases and so also the swelling capacity. The absolute densities of the pure resin and the composites in the hydrated state are less than those in the dehydrated state. In both the states the absolute densities decrease for the pure resin. The attrition effect of the various samples decreases from sample A to F and this is due to the formation of the resin in the capillaries of charcoal particles.

It is observed that the exchange capacities for Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions are greater than those for Na^+ ion for all composites. The sizes of the hydrated ions and Na ions are comparable. Therefore, the higher exchange capacity for the divalent ions, mentioned here, is due to the ionic charge. Among the divalent cations, the exchange capacity increases from Mg^{2+} to Ca^{2+} ion. This may be due to the decrease in the hydrated ionic sizes from Mg to Ca ions. The exchange capacity slowly decreases upto 25% of the charcoal and thereafter the decrease is sudden. Thus it may be concluded that the substitution of charcoal upto 25% results in the exchange capacities as that of the pure resin and hence may be used instead of pure resin for economical reasons.

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Stereochemistry of the Oxime of *N*-Hydroxyimide of β -Naphthol - Maleic Anhydride Adduct

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LANTHANIDE reagents have been used in the stereochemical investigation of organic molecules¹⁻³ including aliphatic and alicyclic ketoximes^{4,5}. Anisotropy of the hydroxyimino group produces large chemical shift differences between *syn*- and *anti*-protons⁶. The effect of anisotropy of oximido group is attributed^{7,8} to the hydroxyl group which deshields the neighbouring protons. In this study, an attempt has been made for the first time to determine stereochemistry of the oxime (1) of *N*-hydroxyimide of β -naphtholmaleic anhydride adduct by nmr study using $Eu(DPM)_3$ as shift reagent. ¹H nmr spectrum of 1 exhibited multiplets at δ 7.27 (4 \times ArH), 4.17 (H-1), 3.90 (H-4), 3.40 (H-2 and H-3), 2.63 (H₁₀-10) and a broad singlet at 3.87 for two hydroxyl protons.

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Successive addition of $Eu(DPM)_3$ in 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.30, and 0.40 *M* equivalent to substrate led to downfield shifts of ¹H signals and the plots of induced downfield shifts ($\Delta\delta$) vs the LSR concentration, $[Eu(DPM)_3]/[substrate]$, for each of H-1, H-10, and H-2 resonances showed linearity (Fig. 1).

TABLE 1 - PARAMAGNETIC SHIFTS OF PROTONS RESONANCES OF COMPOUND 1 AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF $Eu(DPM)_3$

Concn. of $Eu(DPM)_3$ *	$\Delta\delta$			
	H-1	H-2	H-10	H-4
0.05	11	5	3	0
0.10	33	14	9	2
0.15	54	23	15	4
0.20	75	32	21	7
0.30	134	52	33	11
0.40	181	73	46	17

*Concentration in mole ratio of LSR to substrate.

Fig. 1. Plots of induced shifts ($\Delta\delta$) vs metal concentrations, $\text{Eu}(\text{DPM})_3/\text{substrate}$.

The large paramagnetic shift of H-1 relating to H-10 indicates that the hydroxyl group to be *syn* to H-1 as in 1. The fact that the paramagnetic shift of H-2 occurring to a lesser extent than the H-1 also supports the above view.

Experimental

^1H Nmr spectra (60 MHz; CDCl_3) were recorded with TMS as an internal reference on a Varian A-60D spectrometer at 45° , and ir spectrum (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of oxime derivative of β -naphthol-maleic anhydride adduct: β -Naphthol-maleic anhydride adduct prepared⁹, was refluxed with equimolar amounts of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and pyridine in ethanol for 2 h. Crystallisation of solid mass obtained upon addition of water yielded 1, m.p. $170-71^\circ$ (Found: C, 63.03; H, 4.43. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 63.16; H, 4.51); ν_{max} 3 550, 3 200, 1 780, 1 720 and 1 600 cm^{-1} .

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Studies on Thiourea Derivatives. Part-III. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(*N*-thioureidocarbonyl- methoxyphenyl)sulphones

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THIOUREA derivatives have been found to possess wide therapeutic activities¹. Some thioureas have been found to be useful as insecticides². Hence, we have undertaken the preparation of some substituted-phenylthioureas bearing *p,p'*-dihydroxydiphenylsulphone moiety.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone (1) was condensed with chloroacetic acid to get *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2). The acid was refluxed with thionyl chloride to get the acid chloride (3), which was then treated with different

